

In the T. aman season, different densities of RH also caused a gradient of leaf damage: 5–75% at 20 DAT, 5–53% at 30 DAT, 5–65% at 50 DAT, and 14–55% at 70 DAT. Plants apparently recovered from leaf damage by producing new leaves. However, four beetles hill⁻¹ significantly reduced grain yields regardless of the crop stage when the damage occurred. A significant negative correlation between leaf damage and grain yield was apparent (see figure). Plants suffered minor to moderate leaf damage of 0.2–2.0 RH tiller⁻¹, which did not result in significant yield losses (data not shown). Our results also suggest that photoperiod-sensitive rice grown in the monsoon season is more sensitive to yield loss from RH than photoperiod-insensitive rice grown in the summer.

References

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Diurnal distribution of the money spider *Atypena formosana* in the rice plant and its relation to tiller density

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The diurnal vertical distribution of spiders is of interest to understand which prey types *Atypena formosana* (Araneae: Linyphiidae) may encounter over the course of 24 h. In this study, we visually assessed the diurnal distribution of

A. formosana in rice plants and the effect of tiller number on spider number.

Field samplings were done at the IRRI experiment station on clear sunny days with little wind. Initially, we sampled (by using a

sweep net) *A. formosana* at the panicle initiation stage of IR72 at 50 days after transplanting (DAT) on 23 Sep 1999. Temperatures ranged from 23.0 to 31.8 °C, with an average (\pm SD) of 28.5 ± 3.2 °C, and relative humidity (RH, \pm SD)

was $74 \pm 13.8\%$. Sweep netting provides a fast and useful indirect measure of diurnal changes in the proportion of the spider population in the upper portion of the crop, but it is less efficient in sampling arthropods at the lower level. Ten sweep-net samples, each consisting of 10 sweeps, were taken four times over a 24-h period (0600 h, noon, 1800 h, and midnight). We sampled the field diagonally, avoiding sampling any location twice.

Atypena formosana goes through five immature instars, of which the first is completed in the egg sac. Second-instar spiderlings are around 0.8 mm long (Sigsgaard et al, in press; Sigsgaard et al, unpubl.), whereas adults are 1.5–3 mm long, with females being larger than males. A precise determination of a spiderling's instar is difficult, so spiderlings were recorded as small (2d–3d instar), medium (3d–4th instar), or large (4th–5th instar), whereas adults were separated by sex.

In a second experiment, we counted the number of *A. formosana* in the lower, middle, and upper portions of 40 rice plants in each of two plots of IR72 at 30 DAT and one plot of IR72 at 60 DAT, both on 30 Mar 2000. Spiders were counted at 0600 h, noon, 1800 h, and midnight. To compare the observed with the near-actual number of spiders, 10 blower-vac samples were collected in plots. Each sample represented 0.0625 m^2 , equivalent to one hill. Temperatures ranged from 24.0 to $31.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with an average of $28.1 \pm 2.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; RH was $80.5 \pm 14.2\%$. Visual observations were limited to 2 min plant^{-1} during daytime and 3 min plant^{-1} at night, when head lamps had to be used. Rice at 30 DAT is approximately 30 cm tall, so we desig-

nated the first 0–10 cm as the lower portion, the next 10–20 cm as the middle portion, and the last 20–30-cm portion as the top. At 60 DAT, the lower portion was 0–20 cm, the middle was 20–40 cm, and the top was 40–60 cm above the ground. Since visual observations tend to underestimate smaller arthropods, we used the proportion of spiders observed in the middle and top canopies for our analysis.

Tiller number in a rice hill may affect the number of *A. formosana* spiders found, since more tillers may provide a better refuge as well as more prey. We tested this on 80 rice plants of IR72 at 35 DAT on 3 Apr 2000. Temperatures ranged from 24.6 to $31.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with an average of $27.3 \pm 2.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; RH was $82.7 \pm 10.2\%$. Data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance. When requirements for a parametric analysis were met, data were analyzed by ANOVA. For the analysis of visual observations of the vertical distribution of the spider, the proportions of a given class size (small, medium, large) and sex present in the medium and top portions of the canopy were used. Data were arcsine-transformed ($\sin^{-1}\sqrt{y}$) prior to analysis. Since data from the two 30-DAT plots were not significantly different, they were pooled.

The initial sweep netting showed a significant effect of both spider instar and time on number caught (both $P < 0.0001$). Significantly, more spiderlings of all instars were caught at 1800 h than at any other time: 93% of small spiderlings ($n = 258$), 90% of medium spiderlings ($n = 60$), and 88% of large spiderlings ($n = 16$). The number of males and females peaked at midnight, when all males ($n = 3$) and 94% of females

($n = 16$) were caught. Densities of *A. formosana* at 30 and 60 DAT were not significantly different as determined by blower-vac sampling, except for *A. formosana* females (1.9 ± 0.3 females at 30 DAT and 4.0 ± 0.5 females at 60 DAT, $P < 0.001$). At 30 DAT, spiders were observed on the top part of the canopy only at midnight. At 60 DAT, no spiders were observed on the top part (Fig. 1).

Time of day had a significant effect on the proportion of all *A. formosana* observed in the middle and top portions of the canopy at 30 and 60 DAT (both $P < 0.001$). At 30 DAT, the highest proportion of all age classes in the middle and upper parts of the rice plant was observed at midnight. Time had a highly significant effect at 30 DAT on all sizes of spiderlings and for both sexes (all $P < 0.0001$). Pairwise comparisons revealed that, in all cases, significantly more were observed in the middle and top portions of the canopy at midnight at 30 DAT than at the other three times. In addition, more small- and medium-sized spiderlings were observed at 1800 h than at 0600 h (t test, $P < 0.05$). At 60 DAT, the only significant effect of time, when analyzed for age classes separately, was observed among medium- and large-sized spiderlings ($P < 0.002$ and $P < 0.004$, respectively). A higher proportion of these spiderlings was observed in the middle and upper portions of the canopy at 0600 h than at other times of the day (t test, $P < 0.05$). However, actual numbers observed in this portion of the canopy were low.

A significant linear relation was found between tiller number per hill and spider density ($P < 0.0001$) (Fig. 2). Visual counts showed that *A. formosana* had a higher probability of encounter-

Fig. 1. The proportion of small, medium, and large spiderlings and male and female *A. formosana* in the middle and top portions of the rice canopy at (A) 30 d after transplanting (DAT) and (B) 60 DAT. Columns of an age class or sex with different letters are significantly different (t test, $P < 0.05$).

Fig. 2. Linear regression of the number of *A. formosana* over tiller number hill⁻¹.

ing green leafhopper (GLH) than was expected from daytime observations, confirming findings from sweep netting. At 30 DAT, the proportion of all instars in the middle and top parts of the canopy was highest at midnight. The movement up in the canopy at night was less distinct in older, 60-DAT rice, for which only a small proportion of spiders was observed in the middle and top portions of the canopy, > 20 cm above the ground. Both sweep-net sampling at 50 DAT and the counts for rice at 30 DAT found most adults in the upper portion of the rice canopy at midnight. Results for immatures using the two methods differed, with most immatures counted at midnight for 60 DAT and caught with a sweep net at 1800 h for 30 DAT. Differences in sampling method, crop age, or spider biology may account for this. Since the distribution of GLH follows the plant's growth upward, *A. formosana* will encounter fewer GLH in rice at 60 DAT than at 30 DAT. *A. formosana* has an increased probability of encountering BPH and GLH in larger rice hills.

Reference

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